

REPORT

A.2.2.6: Validation of the fitness of purpose of the performance assessment protocol developed in A2.1.4 by demonstrating its applicability for 2 terpenes using TD-GC/MS/FID and the static standards produced in A1.1.2.

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1. Introduction

The BiometCAP project has developed a performance assessment protocol (A2.1.4) for evaluating instruments and methods used for biomethane conformity assessment. Here, this performance assessment protocol was validated using the method ISO 2620:2024 for alpha-pinene, 3-carene and R-limonene. The method is based on thermal desorption followed by gas chromatography with a mass spectrometer and a flame ionization detector (TD-GC/MS-FID). The validation parameters evaluated here were selectivity, limit of detection and quantification, working range and linearity, trueness/bias, and precision. Using these results, the measurement uncertainty was calculated for each component.

2. Materials and methods

The TD-GC/MS-FID instrument was operated in electron impact mode with standard conditions, including an electron energy of 70 eV and a mass scan range from 29 to 300 amu. The analysis utilized a BPX5 column measuring 50 m x 32 mm ID x 1 μm with 5% phenylpolysilphenylene siloxane. Sorbent tubes underwent a two-step thermal desorption process using a Markes TD100 desorber by first heating the tubes to 275 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for seven minutes to release the adsorbed species. These substances were then focused at -10 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in a cold trap containing graphitized carbon before being rapidly heated to 300 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for separation on the GC column. The column effluent was split for detection, with one stream passing through a flame ionization detector (FID) and the other through a mass spectrometer (MS).

A reference mixture produced by NPL in methane as part of activity A1.1.2 containing 3.32 ± 0.1 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$ of alpha-pinene, 3.00 ± 0.1 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$ of 3-carene and 3.18 ± 0.1 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$ of R-limonene was used for the validation.

3. Validation

General overview

The general procedure for determining the performance characteristics of the instrument is summarised in Table 1.

Table 1. Four steps with general procedure for determination of the performance characteristics.

Step	Phase	Description	Results
1	Planning	Specify the components required to be measured by the instrument and the measurement range for each over which the instrument shall be evaluated.	All terpenes, but the validation will be done for alpha-pinene, 3-carene and R-limonene
2	Planning	Establish the functional descriptions of the response functions assumed by the instrument for each specified component.	The response should be linear.
3	Planning	Specify a set of reference gas mixtures (calibration gases) with compositions covering all ranges for all components specified in step 1.	Only one gas mixture will be used: NPL mixture prepared as part of A1.1.2.
4	Planning	Establish the composition and uncertainty of the calibration gas mixture(s) to be used for routine calibration of the instrument.	Ca 3 ± 0.1 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$ per compound

The extent of the performance characteristic validation is summarised in Table 2.

Table 2. Extent of validation.

Performance characteristic	Analytical application		
	Component identification	Component detection	Component quantification
Selectivity	x	x	x
Limit of detection		x	
Limit of quantification			x
Working range			x
Trueness			x
Precision			x
Rise time			Not applicable
Memory effect and fall time			Not applicable

Selectivity

Protocol: To perform the selectivity evaluation, use a reference material containing both the analyte of interest and other components that are expected to be present within the biomethane samples.

Here we used a reference biogas sample containing both the analyte of interest and other components. The selectivity of the method was investigated by studying its ability to measure the analyte of interest in the sample where interferences have been introduced. The method should be optimized to avoid co-elution of the analyte of interest and the other components

present in the sample. Using GC parameters in this method, the following chromatogram was obtained for a biogas sample from a plant digesting food waste (figure 1).

Resolution was calculated according to this equation [1]:

$$\frac{t_{R2} - t_{R1}}{\frac{1}{2}(W_1 + W_2)}$$

Where t_{R2}, t_{R1} are retention time for each peak and W_1, W_2 are width of each peak. A resolution of 1.5 or more occurs when the signal returns to its baseline between two peaks, indicating good separation. Dimethyl-octadiene eluate close to alpha-pinene and calculation of the peak resolution gives a value of 1.1, signifying poor resolution. 1-Methyl-2-piperidinone eluate close to 3-carene with a peak resolution of 1.3, indicating a slight overlap between peaks. Beta-phellandrene and p-cymene eluate close to R-limonene but peaks are well separated with a resolution greater than 1.5.

Figure 1. Gas chromatogram of a biogas from a plant digesting food waste where Dimethyl-octadiene eluate close to alpha-pinene, 1-Methyl-2-piperidinone eluate close to 3-carene and R-limonene shows good separation.

Limit of detection and quantification

Protocol: the LOD and LOQ are calculated in one of two ways: via replicate measurements of blank samples, or via replicate measurements of test samples with a suitably low amount fraction of the analyte. Here we used the second method.

The limit of detection and quantification (LOD and LOQ) for Alpha-pinene, 3-carene and R-limonene was calculated with a Signal-to-Noise (S/N) approach. The S/N ratio is determined by comparing signals from samples with known low amount of analyte with those of blank samples. LOD and LOQ is the determination of the minimum amount at which the analyte can be confidently detected and quantified. The LOD is determined for S/N = 3 and the LOQ for S/N = 10. The results are presented in Table 3. The results show that the method is highly sensitive and can be used to analyze samples with low amount fractions of terpenes.

Table 3. Calculated limits of detection and quantification for terpenes.

Compounds	Target amount ng	Noise	Signal	S/N at target amount	LOD ng (S/N = 3)	LOQ ng (S/N = 10)
Alpha-pinene MS	11.3	850	35900	42	0.80	2.7
3-carene MS	10.2	700	26400	38	0.81	2.7
R-limonene MS	10.8	600	25400	42	0.76	2.5
Alpha-pinene FID	11.3	100	17700	177	0.19	0.64
3-carene FID	10.2	100	15500	155	0.20	0.66
R-limonene FID	10.8	50	15400	308	0.11	0.35

Working range and linearity

Protocol: To assess the instrument working range:

- 1) Identify the **range of interest** (recommended to span $\pm 10\%$ of the expected calibration range) and measure blanks and calibration standards at 6 - 10 amount fractions spread evenly across this range: 10 to 500 ng.
- 2) Plot response against amount fraction and visually examine plot to identify the approximate **linear range**.
- 3) To quantify linearity over the identified **linear range**, measure blanks and calibration standards at 6 - 10 amount fractions spread evenly across the linear range.
- 4) Plot response (y axis) against amount fraction (x axis) and calculate appropriate regression statistics. Plot the residuals (difference in observed y value and predicted by the straight line fit). Random distribution around zero confirms linearity.

Alpha-pinene

The linearity was assessed by analyzing 7 different amounts in nanograms (ng) of alpha-pinene. Results for alpha-pinene measured in the range 11 to 375 ng are shown in Figure 2. As illustrated in Figure 2, the correlation coefficient for alpha-pinene measured with GC-MS/FID is close to a value of 1.00, suggesting that the equation for the linear regression fits the data. This observation implies that the method encompasses a linear working range within 11 to 375 ng.

Figure 2. Correlation between the area measured with MS or FID detector and the known amount of sample in ng.

The distribution of residuals is random, confirming the linearity and working range (figure 3).

Figure 3. The residual of the difference between calculated area and measured area in GC-MS/FID plotted against known amount of sample in ng.

3-carene

The linearity was assessed by analyzing 7 different amounts in nanograms (ng) of 3-carene. Results for 3-carene measured in the range 10 to 339 ng are shown in Figure 4. As illustrated in Figure 4, the correlation coefficient for 3-carene measured with GC-MS/FID is close to a value of 1.00, suggesting that the equation for the linear regression fits the data. This observation implies that the method encompasses a linear working range within 10 to 339 ng.

Figure 4. Correlation between the area measured with MS or FID detector and the known amount of sample in ng.

The distribution of residuals is random, confirming the linearity and working range (figure 5).

Figure 5. The residual of the difference between calculated area and measured area in GC-MS/FID plotted against known amount of sample in ng.

R-limonene

The linearity was assessed by analyzing 7 different amounts in nanograms (ng) of R-limonene. Results for R-limonene measured in the range 11 to 360 ng are shown in Figure 6. As illustrated in Figure 6, the correlation coefficient for R-limonene measured with GC-MS/FID is close to a value of 1.00, suggesting that the equation for the linear regression fits the data. This observation implies that the method encompasses a linear working range within 11 to 360 ng.

Figure 6. Correlation between the area measured with MS or FID detector and the known amount of sample in ng.

The distribution of residuals is random, confirming the linearity and working range (figure 7).

Figure 7. The residual of the difference between calculated area and measured area in GC-MS/FID plotted against known amount of sample in ng.

Trueness, Bias

Protocol, approach 1: **evaluation against a reference material:** compare mean measured value, with the reference value for the reference material. Calculate bias, relative bias, or the relative recovery (apparent recovery)

The differences between the calculated concentrations and the expected concentrations are minimal. Thus, the biases are negligible, as shown in Tables 4, 5, and 6. This indicates that the instrument was pre-calibrated accurately, and no further correction is needed.

Table 4. Bias calculated for Alpha-pinene with FID.

Results μmol/mol	Expected results, μmol/mol	Bias	Relative Bias
18859	18771	88	0
19295	18771	524	3
19125	18771	354	2
19138	18771	367	2
18927	18771	156	2
	Mean	298	1.8

Table 5. Bias calculated for 3-carene with FID.

Results μmol/mol	Expected results, μmol/mol	Bias	Relative Bias
16945	16962	-17	0
17130	16962	168	1
17017	16962	55	0
16999	16962	37	0
16740	16962	-222	-1
	Mean	4	0

Table 6. Bias calculated for R-limonene with FID.

Results μmol/mol	Expected results, μmol/mol	Bias	Relative Bias
17907	17979	-72	0
18055	17979	76	0
17978	17979	-1	0
17902	17979	-77	0
17785	17979	-194	-1
	Mean	-54	-0.2

Precision

Protocol: **To evaluate repeatability** measure the analyte(s) of interest within a reference material at various concentrations spread across the working range using the same method. Obtain at least 10 replicate measurements and calculate the standard deviation and relative standard deviation.

Precision was assessed by measuring 13 duplicates of Alpha-pinene, 3-carene, and R-limonene at varying quantities using TD-GC-MS/FID on several days. Standard deviation, as

well as relative standard deviation, were determined and the pooled standard deviation was calculated. The results can be found in Table 7-12.

Table 7. Estimation of the intermediate precision for Alpha-pinene using TD-GC-FID

Replicates	Meas. 1	Meas. 2	S	CV
1 (240205)	104	103	0.8	0.7
2 (240205)	144	143	0.5	0.3
3 (240205)	213	208	3.2	1.5
4 (240207)	23	24	0.2	0.9
5 (240207)	66	64	1.5	2.4
6 (240207)	138	134	3.2	2.4
7 (240207)	274	266	5.8	2.2
8 (240209)	200	204	2.8	1.4
9 (240209)	287	287	0.2	0.1
10(240209)	434	434	0.0	0.0
11(240209)	576	588	8.1	1.4
12(240219)	113	109	2.2	2.0
13(240219)	203	207	2.3	1.1
			sr%	1.7

Table 8. Estimation of the intermediate precision for Alpha-pinene using TD-GC-MS

Replicates	Meas. 1	Meas. 2	S	CV
1 (240205)	58	57	0.8	1.5
2 (240205)	80	79	0.5	0.6
3 (240205)	120	117	2.4	2.1
4 (240207)	11	11	0.1	0.9
5 (240207)	36	35	0.8	2.4
6 (240207)	78	74	2.7	3.6
7 (240207)	156	149	4.8	3.2
8 (240209)	107	110	1.9	1.8
9 (240209)	162	162	0.5	0.3
10(240209)	251	255	3.0	1.2
11(240209)	331	342	7.6	2.2
12(240219)	64	61	2.1	3.4
13(240219)	114	117	2.1	1.8
			sr%	2.1

Table 9. Estimation of the intermediate precision for 3-carene using TD-GC-FID

Replicates	Meas. 1	Meas. 2	S	CV
1 (240205)	88	86	1.4	1.6
2 (240205)	122	121	0.8	0.7
3 (240205)	180	176	3.5	2.0
4 (240207)	18	17	0.1	0.7
5 (240207)	54	52	1.3	2.5
6 (240207)	115	111	2.8	2.5
7 (240207)	229	221	5.8	2.6
8 (240209)	164	167	2.1	1.3
9 (240209)	240	237	2.4	1.0
10(240209)	359	362	1.7	0.5
11(240209)	483	488	4.2	0.9
12(240219)	97	95	1.4	1.4
13(240219)	178	179	1.0	0.6
			sr%	1.9

Table 10. Estimation of the intermediate precision for 3-carene using TD-GC-MS

Replicates	Meas. 1	Meas. 2	S	CV
1 (240205)	39	38	1.0	2.5
2 (240205)	54	54	0.4	0.8
3 (240205)	82	78	2.6	3.2
4 (240207)	6	6	0.1	1.0
5 (240207)	23	22	0.2	0.9
6 (240207)	51	49	1.7	3.4
7 (240207)	105	101	3.3	3.2
8 (240209)	70	72	1.4	2.0
9 (240209)	110	108	1.0	0.9
10(240209)	171	173	1.7	2.0
11(240209)	228	233	3.7	1.6
12(240219)	44	42	1.0	2.4
13(240219)	81	82	0.6	0.7
			sr%	2.2

Table 11. Estimation of the intermediate precision for R-limonene using TD-GC-FID.

*Calculate without these values (considered as outliers).

Replicates	Meas. 1	Meas. 2	S	CV
1 (240205)	84	83	0.9	1.1
2 (240205)	118	117	0.4	0.4
3 (240205)	173	169	2.8	1.6
4 (240207)	16	16	0.1	0.5
5 (240207)	50	49	0.7	1.5
6 (240207)	107	103	2.4	2.3
7 (240207)	214	206	6.1	2.9
8 (240209)*	148	165	11.9	7.6
9 (240209)*	221	259	27.3	11.4
10(240209)	362	339	16.6	4.7
11(240209)	453	466	8.9	1.9
12(240219)	102	100	1.0	1.0
13(240219)	188	189	0.6	0.3
			sr%	2.1

Table 12. Estimation of the intermediate precision for R-limonene using TD-GC-MS

Replicates	Meas. 1	Meas. 2	S	CV
1 (240205)	28	27	0.8	3.0
2 (240205)	40	40	0.0	0.0
3 (240205)	62	60	1.6	2.6
4 (240207)	4	4	0.0	0.6
5 (240207)	16	15	0.2	1.0
6 (240207)	36	35	1.3	3.6
7 (240207)	77	74	2.5	3.4
8 (240209)	49	51	0.8	1.6
9 (240209)	79	79	0.3	0.3
10(240209)	124	125	0.1	0.0
11(240209)	167	172	3.0	1.8
12(240219)	36	34	1.3	3.6
13(240219)	68	69	0.7	1.0
			sr%	2.4

Measurement uncertainties

The expanded uncertainties ($k=2$) were calculated using the software MUKit. In general, measurement uncertainty of 10% or less are considered reliable. The calculations show that measurement uncertainties are 9% and the method can therefore be considered reliable (Table 13).

Table 13. Within-laboratory reproducibility, method biases and expanded uncertainties from the TD-GC-MS/FID system for terpenes.

Compounds	$u(R_w)$ rel.	$u(\text{bias})$ rel.	$U = 2u_c$
Alpha-pinene	2.49 %	3.41 %	9 %
3-carene	2.62 %	3.31 %	9 %
R-limonene	2.76 %	3.12 %	9 %

4. Conclusions

The validation of the method ISO 2620:2024 for terpenes was performed for alpha-pinene, 3-carene and R-limonene according to the performance assessment protocol written in (A2.1.4). However, only one CRM was used compared to three recommended in the protocol for a linear regression, but the method had previously been validated using 5 different CRM.

ISO 2620:2024 is therefore found to be fit-for-purpose, reliable and highly sensitive. As the working range is at least 10 to 500 ng, it can be used to analyze samples with amount fractions of terpenes from 10 nmol/mol to 5 μ mol/mol (using volumes of 25 to 200 ml per tube).

5. References

[1] Shimadzu, <https://www.shimadzu.com/an/service-support/technical-support/analysis-basics/basic/resol-1.html>